

Brief About Experimental Animals

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Introduction

Laboratory Animal

Laboratory animals are any vertebrate animal (e.g., traditional laboratory animals, agricultural animals, wildlife and aquatic species) produced for or used in research, testing or teaching.

Until such a discovery, animals must continue to play a critical role in helping researchers test potential new drugs and medical treatments for effectiveness and safety and in identifying any undesired or dangerous side effects, such as infertility, birth defects, liver damage, toxicity or cancer-causing potential.

Common Experimental Animals

RODENTS	NON-RODENTS	MISCELLANEOUS
MOUSE	RABBIT	FROG
RAT	DOG	PEGION
GUINEA PIG	CAT	ZEBRAFISH
GEBRILL	MONKEY	CHICKEN
HAMSTER	PIG	

Importance of Laboratory Animal

There are so many questions about animal testing ethics and the animal testing procedures. There are several reasons why the use of animals is necessary for biomedical studies. Animals are biologically very similar to humans. In fact, mice share more than 98% DNA with humans. Animals are susceptible to many of the similar health issues as humans – cancer, diabetes, heart disease etc. Most of experimental animals have shorter life cycle than humans so, they can be studied throughout their life and also across

several generations, a critical element in understanding how a disease processes and how it interacts with a whole, living biological system

Rodents

Mouse

The laboratory mouse or lab mouse is a small mammal of the order Rodentia which is bred and used for scientific research or feeders for certain pets. Laboratory mice are usually of the species *Mus musculus*. Most frequently used, genetics of mammals, virology, models of human disease (mutant strain, transgenic, knockout mice).

Rat

Rats were the first mammalian species specifically domesticated to be used in the laboratory. The rat (*Rattus norvegicus*), is the second most cited animal model used in biomedical research. They are bigger, generally more aggressive and more resistant to various ailments (Johnson, 2012). They are larger in size which makes handling, sampling and performing procedures easier. Rats their small size and rapid reproductive cycle makes them easy to maintain and breed in the laboratory. They are more suited to studies of learning and cognition because they are more capable of learning tasks than mice. Rats have a prevalence within biomedical research second only to humans and they share 90% of the genome with humans (Slusky, 2019).

Types of Rats

Mainly there are four type of laboratory rats are used for various type of animal experiment like Wistar rat Sprague-Dawley rat, Knock-out and Knock-in rat.

Knock-out or Knock-in rat are a genetically engineered rat with a single gene turned off through a targeted mutation (gene trapping) used for academic and pharmaceutical research. Knock-out or Knock-in rats can mimic human diseases and are important tools for studying gene function (functional genomics) and for drug discovery and development. Particularly in “Knock- in rats” there is insertion

of a gene at a specific location on the chromosome while in “Knock- out” rats there is making a gene inoperative which rat strains used to study very specific research questions.

Guinea Pig

Guinea pigs are hystricognath rodents. They belong to the family Caviidae, which contains 14 species of animals commonly known as cavi and Patagonian hares (or maras). Four digits on the forepaw and three on the hindfoot characterize Caviidae. Guinea pigs have a stocky build, large head, short legs, and unfurred, short ears (Quesenberry, 1994).

Uses Of Guinea Pig

Guinea pigs have been used in a variety of studies, including anaphylaxis, asthma, delayed hypersensitivity, genetics, gnotobiotics, immunology, infectious disease, nutrition, otology, and pharmacology and for research in space.

They are used by the pharmaceutical industry for preclinical testing of cardiac safety of new drugs and hairless guinea pigs are used for development and testing of topical drug preparations (Hauser *et al.*, 2005.)

Guinea pigs are also used extensively in the medical device industry for sensitivity testing and as a source of serum complement in laboratories using the complement fixation test to diagnose infectious disease. (Harkness *et al.*, 2002).

Gebrill

Gerbils are also known as jirds or sand rats. The pet and laboratory gerbil are *Meriones unguiculatus*, commonly known as the Mongolian gerbil. Gerbils are quite ratlike. The covering of fur on the tail is short near the base and progressively longer toward the tip so that it is slightly bushy. Coloration of upper parts varies from pale, clear yellowish through sandy and gray. The sides of the body are generally lighter than the back.

Gerbils have a large, ventral abdominal marking gland that is androgen dependent. It attains greater size in males and develops at an earlier age. This gland is used for territorial marking. Females mark their territory at parturition and become more aggressive (Collett *et al.*, 1986).

Uses Of Gebrill

Stroke, Parasitology, Infectious diseases, Epilepsy, Brain development, Behavior and hearing

Hamster

The most common pet and research hamster is the golden or Syrian hamster (*Mesocricetus auratus*). Wild Syrian hamsters have a light, reddish brown dorsal coat, and the underparts are white. The skin of Syrian hamsters is very loose. Dwarf hamster's species commonly used as pets are Djungarian and Roborovsky.

Because of their small body size (< 100 g body weight), hamsters are more difficult to handle and restrain for physical examinations and treatment (Ralph and Menaker, 1988).

Non-Rodents

Rabbit:

Rabbits are small mammals in the family of Leporidae of the order Lagomorpha. Rabbits are commonly used for screening implant material prior to testing in a larger animal model. New Zealand white strains of rabbits are commonly being used for research activities.

These strains are less aggressive in nature and have less health problems as compared with other breeds (Pearce *et al.*, 2007). The most common uses of rabbits in the laboratory are for the production of antibodies, used to detect the presence or absence of disease and for research into infectious diseases and immunology.

Beagle Dog

Dogs (*Canis familiaris*) belong to the family *Canidae* and are thought to be one of the first domesticated animals. Dogs have been very useful research models because they are physiologically quite similar to humans, they also have roughly the same number of genes as humans, and their genome has been sequenced. This makes dogs particularly useful in genetic studies.

Dogs are also known to suffer from similar diseases as humans such as diabetes, epilepsy, autoimmune diseases, cancers, and eye diseases (Serpell *et al.*, 2007). The most common breed of dog used for experiments are beagles, because scientists view them as the best model for human disease. Beagles are convenient to use because they are docile

and small, allowing for more animals to be housed and cared for using less space and money.

Cat

Cat (*Felis catus*) belongs to the family *Felidae* (feline). Although cats are not commonly used in research, cats experience many diseases in a similar

way to humans. Cats also suffer from diseases such as leukaemia, Alzheimer's, heart diseases and infections and immunodeficiency, and therefore, can be great animal models to study them.

Monkey

Monkeys are the closest species to humans in terms of biological make up, with a higher degree of sentience than many other species. Research with monkeys includes advances in transplantation techniques, the role of the Rhesus-factor in blood transfusions, development of in-vitro fertilization techniques, and advances in stem

cell development (Abbott *et al.*, 2003). The most-often used monkeys in medical research are Rhesus macaques (*Macaca mulatta*), Cynomolgus macaques (*Macaca fascicularis*) and Marmosets (*Callithrix jacchus*).

Pig

The pig is increasingly popular as a laboratory animal either as the target species in its own right or as a model for humans in biomedical science. These animals have been used predominantly as preclinical models involving surgical and interventional protocols. Pigs are used in a wide variety of research areas, including agricultural and biomedical studies. They are used as general surgical models, in dermatological studies involving wound healing and plastic surgery procedures, in toxicology and pharmacology studies and in transplantation studies, among other areas of research.

Miscellaneous

Frog

Frogs have been used as research models for many years. Their physiology is relatively simple when compared to mammals. The eggs are opaque but develop into transparent tadpoles within a couple of days so it is easy to study embryonic development. Because the *Xenopus* embryos develop outside of the body they can easily be surgically treated with proteins and chemicals that interfere with development (Nayak, 2010).

Pigeons

Pigeons are a favorite animal to study in the laboratory. Pigeons have excellent visual acuity, color vision, and visual memory, all of which rival or even surpass these abilities in highly visual primates (Levi, 1945). The most commonly used Columbiform in the laboratory is the domestic pigeon. Pigeons possess well-developed powers of navigation and orientation, so are often used in fundamental studies to evaluate the cues used by animals during migration. Their ability to learn to perform tasks in the laboratory has led to their extensive use in behavioral and psychology studies, especially with respect to vision and learning. Pigeons are also used in toxicology, physiology and pathology and in the development of avian medicines.

Zebrafish

Danio rerio the Latin name for zebrafish formerly called *Brachydanio rerio* is a small tropical freshwater fish. Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) can be used in tests investigating fear, stress, and anxiety, learning and memory, and social behavior (Matthews *et al.*, 2002). It has fully sequenced genome, easy genetic manipulation, high fecundity, external fertilization and rapid development, and nearly transparent embryo. Zebrafish are a unique model animal for biomedical research, including studies of biological processes and human diseases.

Chickens

Chickens have been used in research for a long time, they were the first animals to be used to demonstrate inheritance, and they were also the first animals to have their genome sequenced.

